

Hotel Management System

Consider an hotel management system. The client accesses the system through the internet, and can book an hotel room, by choosing both check-in and check-out dates. The dates availability are verified and the reservation is confirmed and stored, if the selected dates are available. When booking a room in that hotel, the client needs to provide his/hers personal details.

Software engineers created an iStar goal model describing the previous scenario (presented on the **right side** of the screen). However, after a management meeting, **a new scenario appeared**:

At check-out, the system calculates the amount to be payed by the client. The payment can be made by using a debit or a credit card. When using a credit card, the client has to pay an extra fee.

Please change the iStar 2.0 goal model describing this scenario, by using the tool on the right. When you finish, click on the button below.

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